

LISTENING AND SPEAKING SKILLS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract:

A farther lingo as a suggests of communication, cognition, a way of tolerating and putting absent information predetermines the got to claim all sorts of talk development. Inside the setting of the integration of Uzbekistani colleges into the European space, data and data of English, especially the progression of talking aptitudes, is ofparamount noteworthiness. One of the issues offluency in English is the require of an fitting tongue environment. To overcome challenges in this locale, it gets to be crucial to apply a certain procedure that progresses useful acing of verbal communication aptitudes. For this reason, the utilize of such strategies as driving questions, pictures, entering unused vocabulary, tuning in to CDs for perusing fabric, watching movement pictures with subtitles shows up fitting. Based on the existing challenges in acing a inaccessible lingo, the article depicts the approaches to two sorts of talk activity, to be particular, talking and tuning in, and illustrates the ways and infers of making aptitudes in a bilingual gathering of individuals.

Key words: recognizable English, communication, talking development, comprehension, nonnative tongue, capacity, methodological issue, appropriate level, acing the aptitudes.

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Introduction

The display worldwide circumstance, data blast, worldwide financial and political integration decide the inclusion a developing number of specialists in different areas of science and innovation within the coordinate usage of worldwide logical and specialized relations went with by critical development and extension of the social and commerce contacts all these show their claims to the nature of remote dialect talking. Terms of foreign dialect communication within the modern world, when a remote dialect could be a implies of

communication, information, accepting and capacity of data, decided the need of owning all sorts of discourse movement: essentially of talking and tuning in. When acing a remote discourse in bilingual circumstance we confront the issue of non-compliance of the used preparing strategies with the cutting-edge prerequisites to acing a outside dialect [1]. We got to bear in intellect that these days college instruction has changed, and the Uzbekistan Colleges have been coordinates within the European Space, so understudies will require a moment dialect to finish their careers. In show disdain toward of the reality that our understudies spend a parcel of a long-time examining English, from school to college, it has been continuously said that English isn't well talked in Uzbekistan

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and a few of the learners can guarantee that they are not competent of talking and communicating fluidly in English.

Methodology

Our individuals are for the most part considered to be great at remote dialects, particularly, when we allude to tuning in and talking aptitudes, as for centuries individuals of distinctive nationalities are living side by side in Uzbekistan and for them talking a few other dialects, in expansion to local, (Russian, Georgian, Lezgin, Talysh, Avar, and a few other) is very a common thing for both children and grown-ups. But as distant as the English dialect is concerned it is still an unsolved matter in our nation. Of course, we must acknowledge that within a long time of autonomy, when the relations with the European nations and the USA impressively extended, various agents of the youthful era, particularly those who have the opportunity of going overseas for ponder and traineeship, can as of now communicate in English very fluidly (0.8% of the populace). By the by, the most noteworthy portion of those learning English as a moment dialect are encountering a few troubles in talking and tuning in whereas acing the dialect. One of the issues why Uzbekistani understudies endure this problem is that when understudies wrap up their English lessons, they disregard the dialect. They are not in contact with the dialect since all the things that encompass them are in Uzbekistani: tv, movies, TV arrangement, talks within the roads, busses, in a word all over in their environment. As it were a few understudies guarantee that they are exceptionally sharp on TV arrangement in English and they observe movies with subtitles. Maybe a presumption that "tuning in may be a reflex, a small like breathing, tuning in rarely gets unmistakable educating consideration in one's local dialect", so tuning in with understanding in a non-native dialect being though complex but exceptionally imperative [3]. The most issues watched by the instructor when understudies are tuning in to English are need of concentration and need of practice. They don't ordinarily prepare their ear and they don't know how to make strides this expertise since they got to get utilized to tune in to English to create their capacities

Result and discussion

When managing with the tuning in handle, it must be specified that there are two conceivable ways of performing this assignment: 1) the Topdown tuning in handle and 2) the Foot up tuning in handle. The previous comprises of understanding the common meaning of a tuning in choice without paying attention to particular structures, words and so on. "It is like a common outline where the audience gets a common see of the tuning in entry whereas still understanding the common thought. Foot up preparing is basically a etymological handle in which we attempt to form sense of acoustic signals by using information of dialect. According to this model, sound is expected to be decoded by accreditation and in a direct fashion- from phonemes, to words, to expressions, to expressions, to total significant writings" [4]. The distinction between them is the taking after: for the Top-down handle, understudies take under consideration the setting and don't got to pay consideration on particular points of interest whereas in Foot up tuning in handle, understudies got to pay consideration since here, particular subtle elements are exceptionally critical to get it the full meaning of the discussion or another kind of listening activity. For this reason, we need to investigate the characteristics of the talking abilities and propose a few ways of practicing talking and giving input. Talking is an "activity requiring the integration of numerous subsystems. All these components

combine to create talking a moment or outside dialect a imposing assignment for dialect learners. Yet for numerous individuals, talking is seen as the central aptitude".

References:

- [1]. Гальскова Н. Д. Современная методика обучения иностранному языку: пособие для учителя. М.: Аркти
- [2]. Bailey and Savage's "New Ways in Teaching Speaking"
- [3]. Lindsay Miller *Second Language Listening: Theory and Practice* Cambridge University Press.
- [4]. Greg S. Baker. *Developing Effective Communication and Social Skills* international scientific journal volume 1 Issue 8 UIF-2022: 8.2 | ISSN: 2181-3337
- [5]. Савицкая Н. С., Даниленко Р. М. Использование аутентичных видеоматериалов при формировании навыков говорения на занятиях по иностранному языку // *Филологические науки*.
- [6]. Мирзаев, Т. А. (2022, September). Ватанпарварлик Туйғуси-Олий Фазилат. In *Conference Zone* (pp. 52-53).
- [7]. Alfrovich, M. T., & Ogli, S. K. S. (2021, August). *Courage of Uzbek people in the battle on the threshold of Stalingrad*. In *Archive of Conferences* (pp. 100-103).
- [8]. Alfrovich, M. T., & Khushnudbek, S. (2021). *Education of students in the spirit of patriotism by studying the history of the great patriotic war*.
- [9]. Nizami, M. T. A. (2021). *The Role of Military Education in Higher Educational Institutions and the Military Field*. *International Journal of Discoveries and Innovations in Applied Sciences*, 1(3), 5-6.
- [10]. Mirzaev, T. A., & Shernazarov, K. S. U. (2021). *The role of military education in higher educational institutions and the military sphere*. *Scientific progress*, 2(2), 604-606.